

Supplementary File 12: Exercise Intensity

Figure S1

In-Task Measures of Perceived Exertion

Note. Rating of perceived exertion during warm up and for each 2.5-min interval, in each condition. Each color represents an individual participant. RPE = rating of perceived exertion; WU = warm up.

Figure S2

Individual Workload During the 5%-Above-Ventilatory-Threshold Phase

Note. Each dot represents an individual participant.